

Weather Forecasting Application using Time Series Analysis

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Abstract— This project entails the development of a weather forecasting application utilizing data from a college's weather station. The core of the application is a machine learning model trained on time series data to forecast temperature, wind, and humidity. Integrated with Flutter for the front end and TFLite for the backend, the application provides users with an intuitive interface for accessing accurate and reliable weather forecasts. Key features include real-time updates sourced from the weather station, interactive visualizations of forecasted data and customizable theme changeable settings for weather alerts. Continuous model refinement ensures forecast accuracy, accessibility, and performance optimization enhance user experience. Feedback mechanisms are also provided for user engagement and assistance. This project aims to deliver a robust and user-centric weather forecasting solution leveraging machine learning and mobile app technologies.

Keywords— machine learning, Time Series Forecasting, temperature, flutter, weather app

I. INTRODUCTION

In an era where access to real-time weather information is crucial for individuals and businesses, the development of advanced weather forecasting applications becomes increasingly significant. This project aims to create such an application by harnessing the power of machine learning to deliver accurate and accessible weather forecasts. Leveraging data from a college's weather station, the application integrates a machine learning model trained on time series data to predict essential weather parameters such as temperature, wind speed, and humidity. By blending cutting-edge technologies with user-centric design principles, the goal is to deliver a weather forecasting model that not only meets users' functional needs but also enhances their overall experience in accessing and interpreting weather information.

II. DATASET

The dataset which is used contains weather data for Juhu, Mumbai, India. This data was taken out from our college's weather station. It contains various features as temperature, pressure, humidity, wind speed, rainfall, etc. But for this project we have used only temperature, humidity and wind speed data. The main target is to develop a prediction model accurate enough for predicting the weather.

III. METHODOLOGY

First, we started analyzing the weather conditions from our dataset – for example, the most common temperature range, temperature and humidity condition throughout the given timeline, etc. Then started performing Time Series Analysis on the data of temperature, followed by humidity and wind speed.

Time Series Analysis comprises methods for analyzing time series data in order to extract meaningful statistics and other characteristics of the data. Time Series Forecasting is the use of a model to predict future values based on previously observed values. Time Series are widely used for non-stationary data like economic, weather, stock price, and retail sales. In this project, we are going to predict temperature, humidity and wind speed with time series forecasting using RNN method.

Basically, our forecasting model comprises multiple Convolutional and LSTM layers. Long Short-Term Memory networks are usually called as “LSTMs” – are a special kind of RNN, which is capable of learning long-term dependencies. They were introduced by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997) and were refined and popularized by many people. Remembering information for long periods of time is practically their default behavior. All recurrent neural networks have the form of a chain of repeating modules of

neural network. In standard RNNs, this repeating module will have a simple structure, such as a single tanh layer.

Fig.1 : Time Series Forecasting Model

First, we are taking two convolution layers with kernel size 2 by 2 in both layers. Then we added a Max Pooling Layer of pool size 2 by 2 to drop some values and take more relevant of them for further process. Then we are Flattening the data and repeating the vectors 30 times to feed in further LSTM layers. Then we are adding a LSTM layer with activation function tanh then adding a dropout layer to drop 20% values and then data goes to further two identical LSTM layers with activation function tanh. Then adding a Bidirectional LSTM layer with activation function relu.

Using bidirectional will run your inputs in two ways, one from past to future and one from future to past so using the two hidden states combined you are able in any point in time to preserve information from both past and future. This can be beneficial for our forecasting model. Then we added a normal ANN layer with activation function with relu activation function and then added an output node to give the output.

We compiled the model with ADAM optimizer. ADAM is a modified version of Stochastic Gradient Descent optimizer and it is proved in many researches that this works really-well with Deep Learning models. The model is trained using 300 epochs, which means the entire dataset is passed forward and backward through the neural network 300 times for learning.

IV.RESULT

```

Model: "sequential"
-----
Layer (type)                Output Shape              Param #
-----
conv1d (Conv1D)              (None, 29, 256)          768
conv1d_1 (Conv1D)            (None, 28, 128)          65664
max_pooling1d (MaxPooling1D) (None, 14, 128)          0
flatten (Flatten)            (None, 1792)              0
repeat_vector (RepeatVector) (None, 30, 1792)          0
lstm (LSTM)                   (None, 30, 100)          757200
dropout (Dropout)            (None, 30, 100)          0
lstm_1 (LSTM)                 (None, 30, 100)          80400
lstm_2 (LSTM)                 (None, 30, 100)          80400
bidirectional (Bidirectional) (None, 256)              234496
dense (Dense)                 (None, 100)              25700
dense_1 (Dense)               (None, 1)                101
-----
Total params: 1244729 (4.75 MB)
Trainable params: 1244729 (4.75 MB)
Non-trainable params: 0 (0.00 Byte)
    
```

Fig.2 : Model Description

The following will be the predicted vs tested graph of our machine learning model:

Temperature Forecasting:

```
✓ 2s from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error
mse = mean_squared_error(Ytesting, predict)
print(f'MSE: {mse}')
```

```
➔ MSE: 0.1256293580382873
```

```
✓ 0s [55] from sklearn.metrics import mean_absolute_error

# Mean Absolute Error (MAE)
mae = mean_absolute_error(Ytesting, predict)
print(f'MAE: {mae}')
```

```
MAE: 0.15425295074306924
```

```
✓ 0s [56] from sklearn.metrics import r2_score
r2 = r2_score(Ytesting, predict)
print(f'R-squared: {r2}')
```

```
R-squared: 0.8559324316241401
```

The temperature prediction model demonstrates strong performance based on the provided evaluation metrics. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) of 0.125629 indicates that, on average, the squared differences between the predicted and actual temperatures are relatively low, suggesting accurate predictions. The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.1542529 further supports this, showing that the average absolute difference between the predicted and actual temperatures is small.

Moreover, the R-squared value of 0.855932 highlights the model's robustness, as it implies that approximately 86 percent of the variance in the actual temperature values is explained by the predictions.

This high R-squared value signifies that the model effectively captures the underlying patterns in the temperature data, leading to reliable and precise predictions.

Humidity Forecasting:

```
✓ [94] from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error  
0s mse = mean_squared_error(Ytesting, predict)  
print(f'MSE: {mse}')
```

MSE: 0.6607453763731668

```
✓ 0s ▶ from sklearn.metrics import mean_absolute_error  
  
# Mean Absolute Error (MAE)  
mae = mean_absolute_error(Ytesting, predict)  
print(f'MAE: {mae}')
```

```
↳ MAE: 0.5581021674447003
```

```
✓ [96] from sklearn.metrics import r2_score  
0s r2 = r2_score(Ytesting, predict)  
print(f'R-squared: {r2}')
```

R-squared: 0.9265861433825272

These evaluation metrics suggest that the model performs quite well in predicting humidity levels. With a mean squared error (MSE) of 0.66074 and a mean absolute error (MAE) of 0.55810, this model demonstrates relatively low error rates, indicating that it accurately predicts humidity values. Additionally, achieving an R-squared value of 0.92658 indicates that a

significant portion of the variance in the data is explained by this model, further validating its effectiveness.

Wind Speed Forecasting:

```
✓ [135] from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error  
1s mse = mean_squared_error(Ytesting, predict)  
print(f'MSE: {mse}')
```

MSE: 7.14367861444042

```
✓ [0s] from sklearn.metrics import mean_absolute_error  
# Mean Absolute Error (MAE)  
mae = mean_absolute_error(Ytesting, predict)  
print(f'MAE: {mae}')
```

MAE: 2.0305014956342706

```
✓ [0s] [137] from sklearn.metrics import r2_score  
r2 = r2_score(Ytesting, predict)  
print(f'R-squared: {r2}')
```

R-squared: 0.7578183516765923

With a mean square error (MSE) of 7.14367 and a mean absolute error (MAE) of 2.030501, model's performance indicates a reasonably accurate prediction of wind speed test data compared to the predicted values. The MSE reflects the average squared difference between the observed and predicted values, with lower values indicating better accuracy. Similarly, the MAE measures the average absolute difference between the observed and predicted values, with lower values indicating closer alignment.

Moreover, the R-squared value of 0.75781 suggests that approximately 75.78 percent of the variability in the wind speed test data can be explained by the model. This indicates a moderate-to-good fit of the model to the data, signifying that a significant portion of the variance in wind speed is captured by the predictive features.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This project illustrates the potential of advanced machine learning models in improving weather forecasting accuracy. The successful integration of multiple Convolutional and LSTM layers, along with the use of state-of-the-art techniques like the ADAM optimizer and Bidirectional LSTMs, showcases a robust approach to handling and predicting non-stationary time series data. This work not only meets the functional needs of users but also enhances their experience in accessing and interpreting weather information, paving the way for more accurate and user-friendly weather forecasting applications in the future.

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